

OSHQOVOQ (*CUCURBITA MOSCHATA DUCHESNE*) NEMATODALARI FAUNASI VA EKOLOGIYASI

To‘xtasinov Farxod Raxmonberdiyevich Farg‘ona davlat universiteti Zoologiya va umumiy biologiya kafedrasida katta o‘qituvchisi b.f.f.d (PhD)
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Annotatsiya. Quyidagi maqolada Oltiariq tumani ayrim fermer xo‘jaliklari sabzavot ekinlari yetishtiriladigan dala qirg‘oqlarida ekiladigan oshqovoq “Palov kadi” navida uchraydigan fitonematodalar faunasi, ekologiyasi, hamda sistematik taxlillari keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Oshqovoq “Palov kadi” navi, Parazit, fitonematoda, ekologik guruh, pararizobiont.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены фауна, экология и систематический анализ фитонематод, обнаруженных в сорте тыквы «Палов кади», высаженной на краях овощных полей некоторых фермерских хозяйств Олтиарыкского района.

Ключевые слова: Сорт тыквы «Палов кади», Паразит, фитонематода, экологическая группа, параризобионт.

Abstract. This article presents the fauna, ecology and systematic analysis of phytonematodes found in the pumpkin variety "Palov kadi" planted on the edges of vegetable fields of some farms in the Oltiaryk district.

Key words: Pumpkin variety "Palov kadi", Parasite, phytonematode, ecological group, pararizobiont.

Nematodalar to‘garak chuvalchanglar – Nematelminthes tipi, haqiqiy to‘garak chuvalchanglar – Nematoda sinfga mansub birlamchi tan abo‘shliqli organizmlar. Ular tabiatda keng tarqalgan bo‘lib, turlar xilma – xilligiga boy guruh hisoblanadi. Hozirgi vaqtda jaxon faunasida nematodalarning 24 mingdan ortiq turi ma‘lum [3]. O‘simlik parazit nematodalari qishloq xo‘jalik ekinlariga salbiy ta‘sir etadi, o‘simliklarni ommaviy nobud bo‘lishiga olib kelishi mumkin va hosildorlikni 60-80 % gacha kamaytiradi [1].

Quyidagi tadqiqot ishlari Farg‘ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani ayrim fermer xo‘jaliklari dala maydonlarida yetishtiriladigan oshqovoq (“Palov kadi” navi) o‘simligi ustida olib borildi. Tuproq va o‘simlik namunalari sabzavot va poliz ekinlari ekilgan dala moydonlari chetki qisimlarida yetishtirilgan oshqovoq o‘simligi ildiz hamda ildiz atrofi tuproqlardan yig‘ildi. Ildiz hamda tuproq namunalaridan fitonematodalar Bermanning voronkali usulida ajratib olindi [3]. Olib borilgan tahlillar natijasiga ko‘ra, oshqovoq o‘simligi poya va barglari, ildizi va ildiz atrofi tuprog‘ida 25 turga mansub nematodalar qayd etildi (1-jadval).

Oshqovoq va uning ildiz atrofi tuprog‘ida aniqlangan nematodalar 4 ta turkumga mansub bo‘lib, ular orasida turlar soni bo‘yicha Teratocephalida turkumi vakillari yetakchi o‘rinni egallab (13 tur), jami aniqlangan turlarning 52,0% ini tashkil etdi. Keyingi o‘rinlarni Tylenchida turkumi (7; 28,0%) egalladi. Aphelenchida (3; 12,0%) va Dorylaimida (2; 8,0%) turkumlari vakillari kam sonda uchradi.

Dorylaimida turkumi 1 ta oila: Qudsianematidae; 1 ta avlod: *Eudorylaimus*; 2 turdan (8,0%) iborat. Jami 3 ta (1,8%) nematoda individlarini o‘z ichiga oladi. Teratocephalida turkumi 2 ta oila: Panagrolaimidae, Cephalobidae; 8 ta avlod: *Panagrolaimus*, *Heterocephalobus*, *Cephalobus*, *Eusephalobus*, *Acrobeloides*, *Chiloplacus*, *Acrobeles*, *Cervidelus*; 13 ta tur (52,0%), jami 91 ta (55,1%) nematodani o‘z ichiga oladi. Aphelenchida turkumi 2 ta oila: Aphelenchidae, Aphelenchoididae; 2 ta avlod: *Aphelenchus*, *Aphelenchoides*; 3 ta tur (12,0%), jami 37 ta (22,4%) nematodani o‘z ichiga oladi. Tylenchida turkumi 6 ta oila: Tylenchidae, Dolichodoridae, Hoplolaimidae, Pratylenchidae, Meloidogynidae, Anguinidae; 7 ta avlod: *Filenchus*, *Aglenchus*, *Bitylenchus*, *Helicotylenchus*, *Pratylenchus*, *Meloidogyne*, *Ditylenchus*; 7 ta tur (28,0%), jami 34 ta (20,6%) nematodani o‘z ichiga oladi.

Eudominant nematodalar – 2 tur (*Panagrolaimus rigidus*, *Aphelenchus avenae*), dominantlar – 1 tur (*Eucephalobus striatus*), subdominantlar – 13 tur (*Cephalobus persegnis*, *Heterocephalobus elongatus*, *Eucephalobus oxyuroides*, *Acrobeloides buetschlii*, *Chiloplacus symmetricus*, *Acrobeles ciliatus*, *Panagrolaimus subelongatus*, *Aphelenchoides parietinus*, *Filenchus filiformis*, *Bitylenchus dubius*, *Pratylenchus pratensis*, *Meloidogyne incognita*, *Ditylenchus dipsaci*) qolgan turlar retsedentlar (6 tur) va subretsedentlar (3 tur)ni tashkil etadi.

Ekologik guruhlar bo‘yicha 5 ta ekologik guruhga mansub bo‘lib, pararizobiontlar – 2 tur (jami turlarning 8,0%), 3 ta (umumiy aniqlangan nematodalarning 1,8%) individ; devisaprobiontlar – 13 tur (52,0%), 91 ta (55,2%); kasallik keltirib chiqarmaydigan fitogelmintlar – 5 tur (20,0%) va 47 ta (28,5%); kasallik keltirib chiqaradigan fitogelmintlar – 5 tur (20,0%) va 24 ta (14,6) individlarni o‘z ichiga oladi. Eusaprobiont guruhi vakillaridan oshqovoq o‘simligida uchramadi.

Pararizobiontlar guruhi Dorylaimida turkumi va Qudsianematidae (umumiy turlar sonining 2; 8,0%) oilasini o‘z ichiga oladi. Devisaprobiontlar guruhi turkumi Panagrolaimidae, Cephalobidae oilalariga oid 13 tur (jami aniqlangan turlarning 52,0%), 91 ta (55,1%) ni tashkil qiladi. Kasallik keltirib chiqarmaydigan fitogelmintlar Aphelenchida va Tylenchida turkumlari, Aphelenchidae, Aphelenchoididae, Tylenchidae, oilalariga oid 5 turni (jami aniqlangan turlarning 20,0%), 47 ta (28,5%) individni o‘z ichiga oladi. Kasallik keltirib chiqaradigan fitogelmintlar – Tylenchida turkumi Dolichodoridae (1; 4,0%), Hoplolaimidae (1; 4,0%), Pratylenchidae (1; 4,0%), Meloidogynidae (1; 4,0%), Anguinidae (1; 4,0%) oilalariga mansub turlardan iborat.

Tahlil natijasiga ko‘ra oshqovoq o‘simligi poya va barglarda nematodalar uchramadi, ildizda – 9 tur (58 ta), ildiz atrofi tuprog‘ida – 21 tur (107 ta) qayd etildi. Aksariyat turlar faqat tuproqda uchradi. Ayrim turlar masalan, *Eucephalobus striatus*, *Panagrolaimus rigidus*, *Aphelenchus avenae*, *Bitylenchus dubius* va *Pratylenchus pratensis* ildiz va ildiz atrofi tuprog‘ida uchrashi qayd etildi (1-rasm).

Oshqovoqda parazit nematodalardan 10 tur qayd etildi, jumladan, 5 turi – *Bitylenchus dubius*, *Helicotylenchus dihystra*, *Meloidogyne incognita*, *Pratylenchus pratensis* va *Ditylenchus dipsaci* kasallik keltirib chiqaradigan fitogelmintlar hisoblanadi.

1-rasm. Zararlangan oshqovoq o‘simligi va ildiz sistemasi.

1-jadval.

Oshqovoq fitonematodalari (Oltiariq tumani “Palov kadi”navi)

№	Nematodalar nomi	Olingan namunalari			Jami
		poya, barg	ildiz	tuproq	
1.	<i>Eudorylaimus monohystera</i>			1	1
2.	<i>E. pratensis</i>			2	2
3.	<i>Cephalobus persegnis</i>			6	6
4.	<i>Heterocephalobus elongatus</i>			6	6
5.	<i>Eucephalobus oxyuroides</i>			4	4
6.	<i>E. striatus</i>		4	11	15
7.	<i>Acrobeloides buetschlii</i>			6	6
8.	<i>A. tricornus</i>			2	2
9.	<i>A. emarginatus</i>		3		3
10.	<i>Chiloplacus symmetricus</i>			5	5
11.	<i>Acrobelus ciliatus</i>		4		4
12.	<i>Cervidelus insubricus</i>			2	2
13.	<i>Panagrolaimus longicaudatus</i>			1	1
14.	<i>P. rigidus</i>		17	15	32
15.	<i>P. subelongatus</i>			5	5
16.	<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i>		15	15	30
17.	<i>A. cylindricaudatus</i>			1	1
18.	<i>Aphelenchoides parietinus</i>		6		6
19.	<i>Filenchus filiformis</i>			7	7
20.	<i>Aglenchus agricola</i>			3	3
21.	<i>Bitylenchus dubius</i>		1	5	6
22.	<i>Helicotylenchus dihystra</i>			3	3
23.	<i>Pratylenchus pratensis</i>		2	2	4
24.	<i>Meloidogyne incognita</i>		6		6
25.	<i>Ditylenchus dipsaci</i>			5	5
Turlar soni:		-	9	21	
Individlar soni:		-	58	107	165

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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A BRIEF REVIEW OF STUDIES ON THE AMPHIPOD (MALACOSTRACA: AMPHIPODA) FAUNA OF THE CHIRCHIK BASIN AND ADJACENT AREAS

Firdavs Fazliddinov¹, Farrukh Umarov², Murat Özbek³

¹ Andijan State University, PhD student of the department of Ecology and botany;
firdavsbiologist@gmail.com

¹ Andijan State University, Docent of the Department of Ecology and Botany, PhD in biological sciences; ecoumarov@gmail.com

³ Ege University, Professor of the department of Inland water biology, Doctor of biological sciences; murat.ozbek@ege.edu
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Annotatsiya. Maqolada Chirchiq havzasi va unga yondosh hududlardagi amfipodalar faunasi, ularning tarqalishi va morfologik xilma-xilligi haqida tarixiy manbalar asosida ma'lumot beriladi. A.V.Martynovning tadqiqotlari asosida aniqlangan turlar keltirilib, mavjud ma'lumotlarning tizimlashtirilmaganligi va yangi tadqiqotlar zarurligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Amfipodalar, Chirchiq havzasi, biologik xilma-xillik, morfologik tavsif, Martynov tadqiqotlari.

Abstract. The article provides information, based on historical sources, about the amphipod fauna of the Chirchik Basin and adjacent areas, including their distribution and morphological diversity. Species identified through the research of A.V. Martynov are presented, and the lack of systematization in existing data as well as the need for further studies is emphasized.

Keywords: Amphipods, Chirchik Basin, biological diversity, morphological description, Martynov's research.

Аннотация. В статье на основе исторических источников представлена информация о фауне амфипод Чирчикского бассейна и прилегающих районов, их распространении и морфологическом разнообразии. Приведены виды, выявленные в результате исследований А.В.Мартынова, подчёркивается фрагментарность существующих данных и необходимость проведения новых научных исследований.

Ключевые слова: амфиподы, Чирчикский бассейн, биологическое разнообразие, морфологическое описание, исследования Мартынова.

Amphipods, representatives of higher crustaceans, are widely distributed in almost all aquatic habitats of the world – including freshwater, brackish, and marine environments – and are especially common in freshwater ecosystems such as rivers, lakes, springs, and reservoirs.

Amphipods play an important role in biological diversity. They serve as a food source for many predatory fish and other aquatic organisms. Due to their affiliation with various ecological groups, they are also used as bioindicators for assessing the condition of aquatic ecosystems. The abundance and species composition of amphipods are directly affected by water quality, pollution levels, and hydrological changes. Therefore, studying them is crucial for ensuring ecosystem stability and conducting effective environmental monitoring.

In Uzbekistan, particularly in the Chirchik Basin, data on the distribution and species diversity of amphipods remain insufficient. Existing information is fragmented, often lacks synthesis, and is not based on systematic scientific analysis.

The earliest information on amphipods was presented in a scientific work published in 1875 by Russian zoologist and professor of the University of Warsaw, V.N.Ulyanin. In this work, based on materials collected by Russian scientist and explorer A.P.Fedchenko from the Samarkand and Tashkent regions, the presence of the species *Gammarus pulex* in Central Asia, particularly in the territory of Uzbekistan, was recorded [1].

The contribution of A.V.Martynov, a prominent zoologist and researcher at the Paleontological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences, to the study of Central Asian amphipod fauna is

particularly noteworthy. His fundamental work «Amphipoda Gammaridea of the running waters of Turkestan» (1935) is considered a key source for the systematic description of the region's aquatic invertebrates.

As a result of A.V.Martynov's research, several new species and morphological forms belonging to the genus *Rivulogammarus* (= *Gammarus*) were identified, each of which was provided with detailed morphological and ecological descriptions [2].

- from the Chimyonsoy River in Tashkent region – *Rivulogammarus turanus* and its morphological form *morpha subnivalis*;
- from the Karabas-tov spring in Turkistan region, Kazakhstan – *R.turanus forma karabasicus*;
- from springs near the village of Galkina (Turkistan region) – *R.subaequalis*, *R.turanus karabasicus morpha excisus*, and *R.subaequalis forma zarudnyi*;
- from the Koylik area of the Chirchik Basin – *R.turanus natio kuilkensis*;
- from flowing waters in the Zhambyl region, Kazakhstan – *R.brevicornis*, *R.turanus* subspecies *coxalis*, and *R. hirsutus morpha hirsutissimus*;
- from springs in Shymkent – *R.gracilis*, later renamed by G. Karaman (1984) as *Gammarus chimkenti*;
- from irrigation canals near Talas, Kyrgyzstan – *R.subaequalis* forma *bianchi*.

An analysis of historical and contemporary studies on the amphipod (Malacostraca: Amphipoda) fauna of Uzbekistan's Chirchik Basin and adjacent mountainous areas indicates that this group of aquatic organisms plays a significant role in the region's ecological stability and biological diversity. The research findings, particularly the scientific legacy of A.V.Martynov, have laid the foundation for the taxonomy and morphological characterization of amphipods in the region.

Below is a modern systematic list of amphipod species from the Chirchik Basin and adjacent areas, compiled based on the literature:

Gammaridae Latreille, 1802

Gammarus Fabricius, 1775

1. *Gammarus turanus* (Martynov, 1935)
2. *Gammarus subaequalis* (Martynov, 1935)
3. *Gammarus brevicornis* (Martynov, 1935)
4. *Gammarus hirsutus* (Martynov, 1935)
5. *Gammarus gracilis* (Martynov, 1935) = *Gammarus chimkenti* (Karaman, 1984)

The regional distribution of findings related to this macrozoobenthic group has been recorded in areas such as Chimyonsoy, Karabas-tov, Galkina, Koylik, Shymkent, and other locations, highlighting the ecological adaptability of amphipods. The morphological differentiation among amphipod species is attributed to their adaptation to hydrological and abiotic conditions. However, the fragmented and unsystematized nature of the existing data calls for a comprehensive reevaluation based on ecological and molecular approaches.

The analysis of this study reveals that the amphipod fauna of the Chirchik Basin and its surrounding regions has not yet been fully explored from a scientific perspective. Existing data are primarily based on historical research and lack systematic precision. While A.V.Martynov's work serves as a foundational source in this field, there is a clear need for new investigations employing modern ecological and genetic methods.

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